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Effect of Different Levels of Rhizobium Inoculation on the Early Growth of Selected Soybean (*Glycine max* L.) Varieties

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ABSTRACT

Soya bean is one of the most important crops in the world and presents great versatility. This study was conducted to investigate the effect of rhizobium inoculations at different levels on the early growth of two Soybean varieties (*Glycine max* L.). The study was conducted at the Botanic Nursery in the Department of Plant Biology, Bayero University, Kano. TGX 1835-10E and TGX 1834-5E Soybean varieties were tested. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. Different levels of rhizobia inoculation were prepared at 0 g/kg, 2 g/kg, 4 g/kg, and 6 g/kg. Data were collected on number of leaves, plant height, leaf area and number of nodules at 14, 28 and 42 days after planting (DAP). The data were analyzed using a two-way analysis of variance at a 5% significance level. The variety TGX 1834-5E recorded the highest number of nodules (12.25), while the variety TGX 1835-10E recorded the highest number of leaves (3.33, 7.92, and 10.92 at 14,28 and 42 DAP), plant height (5.80 cm, 11.71 cm, and 14.48 cm at 14,28 and 42 DAP), and leaf area (12.30 mm, 18.14 mm, and 30.40 mm at 14,28 and 42 DAP). A higher inoculation level of rhizobia (6 g/kg) was found to increase most of the growth parameters assessed, particularly the number of nodules. Inoculation with rhizobia is effective in improving the growth and nodulation of Soybean varieties.

Keywords: Rhizobium, inoculant, Soybean

1. INTRODUCTION

Soybean (*Glycine max* L.) is a type of legume that is widely grown for its edible bean, which has a high protein content and is used in a variety of food products. It is one of the most important crops in the world, both in terms of acreage and total production (Keatinge *et al.*, 2011). One of the reasons for the popularity of Soybeans is their high protein content (Qin *et al.*, 2022).

Soybeans are one of the few plant-based sources of complete protein, meaning that they contain all of the essential amino acids that humans need to obtain from their diet. Additionally, Soybeans are rich in other important nutrients, including fiber, vitamins, and minerals (Erbersdobler *et al.*, 2017). It contains 40 % high quality protein, 20 % edible vegetable oil and a good balance of amino acids (Fekadu *et al.*, 2009; Mahamood *et al.*, 2009).

Nitrogen (N) is the most demanded nutrient by the Soybean crop. It is estimated that it takes 80 kg of N to make 1000 kg of grains. Basically, the N sources available to grow Soybeans are the nitrogen fertilizers and the biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) (Hungria, Campo & Mendes, 2007).

The BNF is the principal source of N for Soybean crops. Bacteria of the Bradyrhizobium genus enter the root via infection of the root hairs, forming nodules (Hungria & Mendes, 2015). Native Rhizobium bacteria in soil are not numerous or effective enough to stimulate biological nitrogen fixation and increase yields and early growth (Hardarson *et al.*, 2003). Soybean production requires good supply of N for high yield. However, like many other annual legumes, the crop could meet most of its N requirement through inoculation with Brady rhizobia (Kumaga and Ofori, 2004).

Rhizobium inoculation can lead to establishment of large Rhizobium in the rhizosphere and improved nodulation and nitrogen fixation even under adverse soil conditions (Seneviratne *et al.*, 2000). Recently, it has been reported that BNF can supply nitrogen which may increase relative growth rate (Salih *et al.*, 2015) and yield of Soybean. Several studies reported significant increase in Soybean growth parameters and grain yield due to inoculation of bradyrhizobial isolates (Kala *et al.*, 2011).

The aim of this study is to determine the effect of Rhizobium inoculation at different levels on the early growth of selected Soybean varieties.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study site and seed collection

The study was conducted in polythene bags of 21 cm × 15 cm at the nursery in the Department of Plant Biology, Bayero University Kano on latitude 11°58'N and longitude 8°30'E with altitude of 44m above sea level. Two varieties of Soybean; TGX-1835-10E (VARIETY 1) and TGX 1834-5E-5E (VARIETY 2) were collected from International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Kano.

2. 2. Rhizobia inoculant

Commercially prepared Rhizobium was obtained from International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Kano. The inoculant was prepared from peat (50%) and aqueous Rhizobium suspension (50%).

2. 3. Seed treatment

Slurry method was used to inoculate the seeds. The sticker solution was prepared by dissolving the contents of the enclosed gum Arabic packet into 200 ml of hot water. The gum Arabic serve as an adhesive to enable the inoculants to stick to seeds. The inoculants were thoroughly mixed with the gum Arabic solution and stirred vigorously before sprayed onto seeds.

2. 4. Experimental design

The experiment was laid in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with the application of Rhizobium inoculumat different levels. The levels of application were 0g/0.003kg which serve as the control treatment, 2g/0.003kg, 4g/0.003kg, and 6g/0.003kg. The treatments were randomized and placed in 3 replications. The experiment was terminated at 42 days after planting.

2. 5. Experimental procedure

All pots were subjected to uniform condition with non-limiting water application. Sowing was done on the 19th of January, 2023. Three healthy seeds of uniform size were planted per pot and thinned to one plant per pot of comparable height and vigor at 2 weeks after planting. Tags and labels were assigned to each pot. Routine management practices such as watering with distilled water were carried out until termination of the experiment.

2. 6. Data collection

Data was taken at 14, 28 and 42 days after planting. Number of leaves was taken by direct counting, plant height was measured using meter rule from shoot base to tip of meristem region, leaf area was measured using leaf area meter (LAM-B) and number of nodules was taken by harvesting the roots at 42 days after planting, washing away the soil and counting the nodules on each root.

2. 7. Data analysis

Data collected were presented as means of the 3 replicates used. Two way analysis of variance was used to determine the differences across means at 5% ($p = 0.05$) level of significance. Fisher LSD procedure at 0.05 probability level was used to separate the means that are significantly ($p \leq 0.005$) different.

Table 1. Effects of different levels of Rhizobium inoculation on the number of leaves of two Soybean varieties.

Source	14 DAP	28 DAP	42 DAP
Varieties			
TGX 1835-10E	3.33 ^a	7.92 ^a	10.92 ^a
TGX 1834-5E	2.75 ^b	6.42 ^b	11.25 ^a

Treatments (g/kg)			
0	1.67 ^c	4.83 ^c	7.67 ^c
2	2.83 ^b	6.67 ^b	7.67 ^c
4	3.83 ^a	8.33 ^a	13.5 ^b
6	3.83 ^a	8.33 ^a	15.5 ^a
Interaction			
Variety*treatment	***	***	***

Keys: Means with different letters (a, b, c, d, etc.) in the column indicate statistically significant differences between the treatments (p<0.05). *** significant at 99%. DAP = Days after planting.

Table 2. Effect of different levels of Rhizobium inoculation on the Plant height (cm) of two Soybean varieties.

Source	14 DAP	28 DAP	42 DAP
Varieties			
TGX-1835-10E	5.80 ^a	11.71 ^a	14.48 ^a
TGX 1834-5E	3.17 ^b	8.00 ^b	13.96 ^a
Treatments (g/kg)			
0	1.92 ^b	6.00 ^b	10.03 ^d
2	5.42 ^a	9.92 ^a	11.08 ^c
4	5.18 ^a	11.08 ^a	15.58 ^b
6	5.42 ^a	12.42 ^a	20.22 ^a
Interaction			
Variety*treatment	***	NS	***

Keys: Means with different letters (a, b, c, d, etc.) in the column indicate statistically significant differences between the treatments (p<0.05). *** significant at 99%. DAP = Days after planting.

Table 3. Effect of different levels of Rhizobium inoculation on the leaf area (mm) of two Soybean varieties.

Source	14 DAP	28 DAP	42 DAP
Varieties			
TGX 1835-10E	12.30 ^a	18.14 ^a	30.40 ^a
TGX 1834-5E	11.09 ^b	16.27 ^b	15.60 ^b
Treatments (g/kg)			
0	6.97 ^c	12.75 ^d	17.05 ^c
2	12.30 ^b	15.94 ^c	18.38 ^c
4	11.28 ^b	17.38 ^b	19.88 ^b
6	16.25 ^a	22.73 ^a	36.71 ^a
Interaction			
Variety*treatment	***	***	***

Keys: Means with different letters (a, b, c, d, etc.) in the column indicate statistically significant differences between the treatments ($p < 0.05$). *** significant at 99%. DAP = Days after planting.

Table 4. Effect of different levels of Rhizobium inoculation on the number of nodules of two Soybean varieties.

Source	Number of nodules
Varieties	
TGX-1835-10E	10.50 ^b
TGX 1834-5E	12.25 ^a
Treatments (g/kg)	
0	6.67 ^c
2	6.00 ^c
4	10.83 ^b

6	22.00 ^a
Interaction	
Variety*treatment	***

Keys: Means with different letters (a, b, c, d, etc.) in the column indicate statistically significant differences between the treatments ($p < 0.05$). *** significant at 99%. DAP = Days after planting.

Figure 1. Gum Arabic dissolved in 200 ml of hot water.

Figure 2. 100% germination of seeds treated with 4g and 6g of rhizobium.

Figure 3. Highest root nodules recorded at 6g.

Figure 4. Highest root biomass recorded at 6 g/kg.

Figure 5. Highest number of leaves recorded by plant inoculated with 6g of rhizobium.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Number of leaves

The Results on the effects of different levels of Rhizobium inoculation on the number of leaves of two Soybean varieties and the interaction effect between the treatment and Soybean varieties are presented in Table 1. At 14, 28 and 42 days after planting (DAP), significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed between the treatments and Soybean varieties. Result revealed that Soybean varieties treated with 4g and 6g of Rhizobium at 14, 28, and 42 DAP recorded the highest number of leaves (3.83, 8.33, and 15.5 respectively) followed by 2.83, 6.67, and 7.67 respectively in 2 g/kg, while those treated as controls recorded the least number of leaves (1.67, 4.83 and 7.67 respectively). At 14 and 28 DAP the variety TGX1835-10E recorded the highest number of leaves (3.33 and 7.92 respectively).

Interaction between treatments and varieties showed that at 14 DAP, TGX1834-5E recorded the highest number of leaves at 4 g/kg and 6 g/kg. At 28 DAP, TGX1835-10E recorded the highest number of leaves at 2 g/kg, and at 42 DAP, TGX 1834-5E recorded the highest number of leaves at 6g/kg. However, TGX 1834-5E recorded the least number of leaves at 2 g/kg.

3. 2. Plant height

The Results on the effects of different levels of Rhizobium inoculation on the plant height of two Soybean varieties and the interaction effect between the treatment and Soybean varieties are presented in Table 2. At 14 and 42 days after planting, significant differences ($p < 0.05$)

were observed between the treatments and Soybean varieties. Results revealed that Soybean varieties treated with 6g of Rhizobium at 14 and 42 DAP recorded the highest plant height (5.42, 20.22), while those treated as controls (0g) recorded the least plant height (1.92 and 10.03). At 28DAP, no significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed among the treatments. At 14, 28, and 42DAP, the variety TGX1835-10E recorded the highest plant height (5.80, 11.71 and 14.48).

Interaction between treatment and varieties showed that at 14DAP, TGX 1835-10E recorded the highest plant height at 6g while TGX 1834-5E recorded the least plant height at 0g. At 42DAP, TGX 1834-5E recorded the highest plant height at 6g. However there is no interaction effect between the treatments and Soybean varieties at 28DAP.

3. 3. Leaf area

The Results on the effects of different levels of Rhizobium inoculation on the leaf area of two Soybean varieties and the interaction effect between the treatment and Soybean varieties are presented in Table 3. At 14, 28 and 42 days after planting, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed between the treatments and Soybean varieties. Results revealed that Soybean varieties treated with 6g/kg of Rhizobium at 14, 28, and 42 DAP recorded the highest leaf area (16.25, 22.73, 36.71), followed by those treated with 4g/kg (11.28, 17.38, 19.88), while those treated as controls recorded the least leaf area (6.97, 12.75, 17.05). The variety TGX1835-5E recorded the highest leaf area.

Interaction between the treatments and varieties showed that, at 14 DAP, TGX 1834-5E recorded the highest leaf area at 6g/kg). At 28 DAP, TGX 1834-5E recorded the highest leaf area at a concentration of 6g/kg). At 42 DAP, TGX 1835-10E recorded the highest leaf area at 6g/kg of Rhizobium, TGX 1834-5E recorded the least leaf area at 0g/kg.

3. 4. Number of nodules

The Results on the effects of different levels of Rhizobium inoculation on the number of nodules of two Soybean varieties and the interaction effect between the treatment and Soybean varieties are presented in Table 4. At 42 DAP, significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed between the treatments and Soybean varieties. Results revealed that Soybean varieties treated with 6g/kg of Rhizobium recorded the highest number of root nodules (22.00), followed by those treated with 4g/kg (10.83), while those treated with 0g/kg and 2g/kg recorded the least number of nodules (6.67 and 6.00). The variety TGX1834-5E recorded the highest root nodules. Interaction between treatment and variety showed that TGX 1835-10E recorded the highest number of nodules at 6g/kg (23.33).

4. DISCUSSION

According to various studies, Rhizobium inoculation has been shown to boost legume growth, nutrition, and production and has been regarded as a sustainable and affordable method for supplementing plants' nitrogen needs (Tena *et al.*, 2016). The influence of various Rhizobium inoculation levels and their capacity to encourage the early growth of a chosen Soybean variety were investigated in this study. In comparison to un-inoculated treatments, the study demonstrated that Rhizobium inoculation had a beneficial impact on plant vegetative

growth that include number of leaves, plant height, leaf area and number of nodules. In all of the growth parameters assessed, the un-inoculated treatments exhibited relatively poor growth. Similar findings indicate that an increase in plant growth after bacteria treatment may be caused by the synthesis of phytohormones and the enhancement of nutrient availability (Gholami *et al.*, 2009, Ghorbanpour *et al.*, 2013).

After Rhizobium was inoculated, the quantity of leaves greatly increased. This outcome is comparable to that of Sajid *et al.*, (2010), who reported that the maximum number of leaves observed in inoculated groundnut seeds may be attributed to the symbiotic relationship between Rhizobium bacteria and the roots of leguminous crops, which fixes the atmospheric nitrogen into the roots of groundnut and thus increases the number of leaves. The capacity and uptake of nitrogen, phosphate, and potassium by plants in soil, which positively affect vegetative growth, could also be responsible for the considerable increase in the number of leaves (Abdulkadir *et al.*, 2022).

The findings of this study also show that treatments had a substantial impact on plant height. When compared to the control, the inoculated plants had the highest plant height. Similar findings were observed in the work of Sajid *et al.* (2010), who hypothesized that the sufficient nitrogen fixed by the Rhizobium may be the cause of this. The inoculated plants' increased plant height may also be positively influenced by more leaves per plant.

Treatments also had a positive effect on the leaf area. This is similar to the soybean research of Ishaq *et al.* 2022 who reported that the increase in the leaf area is due to the enhancement of nutrient availability to supplement tissue development. Similarly, the study demonstrated a considerable increase in the number of nodules with increasing inoculation level. The inoculated plants generated the most nodules per plant, whereas the control plants produced less nodules. This result is consistent with the groundnut research of Sarhad *et al.* (2010), who suggested that the increase in nodules in the inoculated plants may be due to the synthetic inoculation of Rhizobium, which increased the amount of bacteria and consequently caused the production of more nodules per plant as inoculation levels were raised.

5. CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated how the two varieties of Soybean reacted to Rhizobium inoculation. The vegetative growth parameters (number of leaves, plant height, leaf area and number of nodules) all increased with rhizobium inoculation and the concentration of 6 g/kg had the highest impact. The bulk of the investigated growth traits were found to have the greatest values in the variety TGX 1835-10E (variety 1) except in number of nodules where TGX 1834-5E (variety 2) had more. It can be said that inoculating Soybeans with rhizobium has a considerable impact on vegetative growth and nodulation in Soybean

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